

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

LIFE OF MUSLIMS IN THE PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF CHINA (1949-2000 YEARS)

Ernazarov O.

*PhD in History, Associate Professor,
UNESCO Chair on religious studies and the comparative study of world religions,
International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan*

Abstract

The article provides information about the social, political and cultural life of Muslim communities in China after the period of imperialism. The article analyzes the results of the centralized solution of the needs of Muslims in the country through the activities of the Chinese Islamic Association.

Keywords: Tang dynasty, Song dynasty, Yuan dynasty, Ming dynasty, Qing dynasty, "religion of Hui", Emperor Xianzong.

From the time Islam entered China until the founding of New China in 1949, Chinese Muslims experienced various situations. Muslims (especially in the Northwest) faced many hardships during the Qing dynasty and the Provisional Military Government. After the founding of New China in 1949, the people's government pursued policies based on ethnic equality and religious freedom. The government has guaranteed a new life and economic, political, ethnic and religious freedom for Muslims of different nationalities in the country. According to the 2000 census, more than 20 million Muslims live in the territory of the People's Republic of China. They mainly lived in Xinjiang, Ningxia, Gansu, Qinghai, Yunnan, Henan, and also in Shanghai, Hebei and Shandong provinces.

After the founding of New China in 1949, Muslims of all ethnic groups in the country were guaranteed equal political and religious freedom, enshrined in the constitution. In order to stabilize the social order and restore the economy, the people's governments in the regions paid attention to the protection of religious attributes such as mosques, mausoleums, and respect for Muslim faith, traditions, and holidays. For example, the State Council, which were responsible for coordinating the organization of holidays and festivals of ethnic minority groups in the country, has declared Ramadan and Eid al-Adha as holidays for all Chinese Muslims. In addition, the Council of State decided to exempt Muslims from the tax on sheep and cattle used for sacrifice during various festive events. In addition, the Ministry of Finance issued an instruction that the land allocated for the construction of mosques and mausoleums should be exempted from land tax.

The following system of regional autonomy was established in areas where Muslims were the majority: Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region (established on October 1, 1955), Changji Hui Autonomous Region in Xinjiang (November 27, 1954), Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region (October 20, 1958), Zangjiachuan Hui Autonomous County in Gansu (July 1, 1953), Menyuan Hui Autonomous County in Qinghai (December 19, 1953), Hualong Hui Autonomous County (March 2, 1954), Dachang Hui Autonomous County in Hebei

(December 7, 1955) [4 : 47]. In this way, all the Muslims in the country started to solve their personal issues independently to a certain extent.

The changes in the life of Muslims in China included the implementation of land reform along with the acquisition of certain political rights. At the initial stage, the Muslims in the villages had no other opportunities except political rights. Like the land reform carried out in the territories belonging to the Hans, Muslims also wanted to implement land reform in their own territory. In response to the wishes of the Muslims, the people's government began to implement land reform based on the opportunities of the areas where the Muslims were the majority. Some time after the land reform, Muslims began to make a significant contribution to the development of the country, along with the effective establishment of agriculture in their respective areas.

In the integration of Muslims into the life of the country, it was important to solve the issues that arose among them centrally within the framework of religious organizations. In 1952, influential Chinese Muslim representatives, including Baoerhan Shahidi, Liu Geping, Saifudin Azizi, Da Pusheng and Ma Jian, united to form the China Islamic Association. These individuals introduced this plan to Islamic circles and ordinary Muslims in the country. In 1952, appointed representatives from various ethnic groups met in a preparatory meeting and formed a preparatory committee to establish the China Islamic Association. In this situation, Baoerhan Shahidi was appointed as the director, Da Pusheng as the assistant director, and the other 27 people were appointed as committee members.

From the founding of the People's Republic of China until 1952, the members of the "preparatory committee" were sent on a pilgrimage to inform the world about the conditions created for Muslims in the country, as well as to establish friendly relations with the Muslims of the world. The members of this delegation consisted of 16 people selected from among the Muslims of the whole country, in addition to the president of the association, Imam Da Pusheng (Hui) and vice-president Yiming Mahesum (Uyghur). The delegation tour, which began in August 1952, ended early

due to the failure to establish diplomatic relations with Saudi Arabia [1 : 82].

In April 1955, Imam Da Pusheng, the vice president of the Chinese Islamic Association, attended the "Bandung Conference" in Bandung, Indonesia as a religious adviser to Prime Minister Zhou Enlai. The Bandung Conference was considered a great success in the history of Chinese diplomacy [5 : 94]. As a result of Prime Minister Zou Enlai's successful negotiations with Egyptian President Nasser and King Faisal of Saudi Arabia, Imam Da Pusheng and the first delegation of pilgrims from New China (19 people) visited Mecca to perform Hajj in August 1955.

In July 1957, the first issue of the magazine "Muslims in China" devoted to various issues was published in Beijing by the Chinese Islamic Association. In this magazine, along with introducing the activities of the association to the Muslims of the country, articles were published about the life and lifestyle of Muslims. It also acted as a mediator for the exchange of information and experiences between local Islamic associations and ordinary Muslims in different regions. Its activity was stopped in 1959, when the 24th issue of the magazine was published.

On November 21, 1955, the Islamic Institute of China was established in Beijing. The students of the institute consisted mainly of promising young Muslims who received a certain level of education in mosques. The following subjects are taught at the institute: Aqidah (theology), Tajweed, Hadith, Fiqh and Arabic literature. In addition, Chinese language (mainly in Uyghur classes), history, geography and politics are taught as secondary subjects at the institute.

In the early and mid-1950s, much attention was paid to the study and publication of Islamic literature. Even an Arabic edition of the Holy Qur'an was copied three times and a number of selected works were lithographed by the Chinese Islamic Association. In 1950, Peking University Press published Ma Jian's translation of the Holy Qur'an. With the efforts of the Chinese Islamic Association, during this period, many publishers published works such as "The Life of Chinese Muslims", "Islam in China" and "The Religious Life of Chinese Muslims" with titles written in Chinese, Arabic, English, French and Malay [2 : 184]. Also during this period, the constitution of the People's Republic of China was translated into Arabic. Despite the scientific and literary development, in the autumn of 1958, under the influence of "leftist" views, Islamic teachings, the study of the history and culture of Chinese Muslims, and the publication of religious literature were suspended for 18 years, that is, until the Cultural Revolution in 1976.

After the Third Plenary Session of the Eleventh Party Central Committee, the Central Committee of the Communist Party, the State Council, the Party Committees, and various authorities tried to abolish the order of chaos that had arisen during the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976). In the course of this process, the names of Muslims who were accused of various crimes during the past period were vindicated and their reputation was restored. The activities of a number of Islamic organizations have been resumed.

The revival and reopening of religious places was an important step in the implementation of the policy of religious freedom. As a result of this reform, 64 mosques opened in Beijing, 53 in Tianjin (including the Hui service center), and 6 in Shanghai. By the end of the 1980s, there were 2,800 mosques, 80 mausoleums, 5 khanaqahs (a place where menhuan (sect) representatives gather and perform certain rituals), 2,900 imams in Gansu; 118 mosques in Shaanxi; 2,700 mosques and 3,600 imams Ningxia; 867 mosques and 3,562 imams in Qinghai; 20,000 mosques in Xinjiang. According to national statistics of registration of religious places conducted between 1994-1996, 34014 mosques were registered across the country. Of these, there were 23,331 mosques in Xinjiang, 2,610 in Gansu, 2,984 in Ningxia, 817 in Henan, 728 in Yunnan, 397 in Hebei, and 409 in Shandong [6 : 96]. In the first decade of the 21st century, the number of mosques in the country remained approximately this amount.

In June 1982, the Islamic Institute of China began accepting a limited number of students again. Not only high-level, but also short-term education courses were opened there. By early 2000, 512 students from eight ethnic groups in the country (including Uyghur, Kazakh, Kyrgyz) graduated from the institute. On the other hand, since 1983, 8 Islamic institutes have been established in Shenyang, Lanzhou, Inchuan, Beijing, Xining, Urumqi and Kunming.

On September 25, 1981, the activity of the magazine "Islam in China" was restarted. In 1983, with the support and efforts of several hundred thousand people, the first bimonthly issue in Uyghur was published. In 1980, Ma Jian's complete translation of the Holy Qur'an was published by the China Social Science Press [8 : 225]. In 1986, using this version, the King Fahd Holy Qur'an Printing Complex printed an Arabic-Chinese version of the Qur'an, which became the most popular version of the Qur'an in Chinese.

Offices dealing with ancient books of ethnic minority groups have been established in some provinces, autonomous regions and municipalities, and many ancient Islamic works have been published. In 1980, the Chinese Islamic Association, in cooperation with several publishers, published the Holy Qur'an in 160,000 copies, "Mukhtasar Tafsir", "Masterpieces of Hadith", Hadith collections of Imam Bukhari and Imam Muslim, "Kutubah", "Life of the Prophet Muhammad", "Islam" translated by Ma Jian. source illustration', published works such as 'Nine Years in Mirs' written by Pang Shikian.

In the 1980s and 1990s, the level of literacy of Chinese Muslims continued to grow. By the beginning of 2000, about 30,000 Muslim students studied in 21 universities and colleges in Xinjiang, and about 10,000 in 7 colleges in Ningxia [6 : 61]. Since 1987, the policy of open dialogue with the outside world has increased the number of Muslims working in various spheres of government, people's congress and consultative political bureaus.

The introduction of Islam to China dates back to the middle of the 7th century. During 1,300 years, that is, during the reign of the Tang, Song, Yuan, Ming, and

Qing dynasties, as well as during the Republican administration (1912-1949), the number of Muslims in China reached 20 million people [3 : 52].

Islam has been called by several names at different times: during the Tang Dynasty (618-907) "Dashi Jiao" ("Dashi" refers to the Arabs, therefore, in the Tang Dynasty, Islam was called "the religion of the Arabs" in the language of the local population), during the Ming Dynasty (1368-1644) "Tianfng Jiao" (Religion of Arabia) or "Hui Hui Jiao" (during this period, all ethnic groups belonging to the Islamic religion were called "Hui" in general, so the term "Religion of the Hui" was widespread in relation to Islam), during the end of the Ming Dynasty and the beginning of the Qing Dynasty (1616-1911), Qingzhen Jiao (Pure and True Religion), during the Republican period (1912-1949) "Hui Jiao" (the term "Hui religion" was applied to the Dungsans, a Muslim ethnic group in China).

After the establishment of the People's Republic of China in 1949, in 1956 the State Council issued the "Notice Concerning the Name of Islam", which stated the following: "Islam is a world religion. "Islam" is the general international term used for this religion, since it should not be called "Hui religion" but simply "Islam" [7 : 147]. After that, the concept of "Islam" began to be used in general throughout China. To date, ten of China's 56 ethnic groups have adopted Islam as their national religion. These are Dungan (Hui), Uyghur, Kazakh, Dunsyan, Kyrgyz, Salar, Tajik, Uzbek, Baoan and Tatars. At the same time, a small number of Muslims also live among the Mongols, Tibetans, Bai, and Dai in China.

Islam had a great influence on the social life of China, especially on the social development of the

above-mentioned ethnic groups. Consequently, Muslims in China are still contributing to the political, economic and cultural development of the country.

References

1. Atwill, David G. *The Chinese Sultanate: Islam, Ethnicity, and the Panthay Rebellion in Southwest China, 1856-1873.* – Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2005.
2. Benite, Zvi Ben-Dor. *The Dao of Muhammad: A cultural history of Muslims in late imperial China.* – Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2005.
3. Benson, Linda. *The Ili Rebellion: The Moslem challenge to Chinese authority in Xinjiang 1944-1949.* – New York: ME Sharpe, 1990.
4. Dillon, Michael. *China's Muslim Hui Community: Migration, Settlement and Sects.* – Surrey: Curzon Press, 1999.
5. Israeli, Raphael. *Islam in China: religion, ethnicity, culture, and politics.* – Lanham: Lexington Books, 2002.
6. *Islam in China / Written by Mi Shoujiang and You Jia; Translated by Min Chang.* – China intercontinental Press, 2004.
7. Gillette, Maris Boyd. *Between Mecca and Beijing: Modernizations and Consumption Among Urban Chinese Muslims.* – Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2000.
8. Gillette, Maris Boyd. *Between Mecca and Beijing: Modernizations and Consumption among Urban Chinese Muslims.* – Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2000.